

Management of Male Infertility in Nigeria: Thinking outside the box

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Infertility is a reproductive health problem that affects many couples in the human population. Worldwide infertility is generally reported as occurring in 8-12% of all couples. Many reports indicate that infertility is the most frequent reason for gynaecological consultation in Nigeria [1-2]. The male factor was found to be responsible for the infertility in 42% of the subjects. Oligozoospermia and asthenozoospermia were the most common aetiological factors responsible for male infertility [3]. Although there is a general documented belief that the most common cause of infertility in Nigeria is infection [4], cases abound where infection have been treated without correction of infertility [5]. In view of the rising trend of male infertility in Nigeria, there is a need for reproductive health physicians to have an expansive approach in their diagnosis of male sterility.

Nigeria has about twelve million infertile persons [5]. In Nigeria there are higher rates of irreversible oligospermia or azospermia than most other causes of infertility and less resources for the management of infertility [6]. Of adult couples in African countries, it is estimated that 10–25% are subfertile and of these subfertile couples female factors account for about 55% and male factors for about 30–40% of causes, while 5–15% of causes are unexplained [5]. In their study, Geidam et al 2008 [7] noted that 70.8 percent of men investigated for infertility had primary infertility and 75 percent had azospermia, 66.7 percent had elevated follicle-stimulating hormone levels, while 50 percent had decreased testosterone levels. The majority (70.8%) of the patients in the study population were found to have primary infertility, which was similar to the study from the southeastern part of Nigeria, [3] and another study from a developed country [8]. However, a report from Ile-Ife in southwestern Nigeria showed a preponderance of secondary infertility [9].

Akinloye et al 2006 [10] study in a Nigerian population reported that high plasma cadmium level can be a cause of oligo-astheno-tetratozoospermia syndrome. Preliminary result of an ongoing study in Nigeria showed that 83.97% of the patients with history of herbal intake had abnormal seminal fluid analysis while only 16.03% of subjects with no history of herbal

intake had abnormal result [11]. This gives a clue of the possibility of male infertility from Nigerian herbal remedies which has been reported to contain heavy metals [12].

Decreasing sperm counts are attributed to the deleterious effects of environmental contamination by heavy metals and estrogenic chemicals [13]. Some heavy metals like lead and cadmium could adversely affect the male reproductive system; either by causing hypothalamic-pituitary axis disruption or by directly affecting spermatogenesis, resulting in impaired semen quality [14]. Several metals especially lead and cadmium are considered reproductive toxicants and/or suspected endocrine disruptor compounds. Jurasovic et al; 2004 [14] have reported positive associations between blood cadmium concentrations and follicle stimulating hormone FSH and testosterone levels among men with no occupational exposure. Several studies have reported declines in semen quality associated with both lead [15] and cadmium concentrations in blood [16]. Other reports have shown an association between impaired sperm motility and cadmium and/or lead concentrations in sperm or seminal fluid [17].

In their investigations on whether heavy metal pollution affects semen quality in men, Giaccio et al. 2012 [18] concluded that Authorities responsible for public health should be aware of potentially insidious effects of environmental pollution on male fertility. Lead and cadmium may be implicated in male infertility in Nigeria. Educational, dietary interventions and inclusion of heavy metal diagnosis may be useful in the management of male infertility.

REFERENCES:

1. Umeora OU, Mbazor JO, Okpere EE. Tubal factor infertility in Benin City, Nigeria - sociodemographics of patients and aetiopathogenic factors. *Trop Doct.* 2007; 37(2):92-4.
2. Orhue A, Aziken M. Experience with a comprehensive university hospital based infertility program in Nigeria. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet* 2008; 101:11-5.

3. Ikechebelu JI, Adinma JI, Orié EF, Ikegwuonu SO. High prevalence of male infertility in southeastern Nigeria. *J Obstet Gynaecol* 2003; 23:657-9.
4. Cates W, Farley TMM, Rowe PJ. Worldwide patterns of infertility, is Africa different? *Lancet* 1985; 2:596-8.
5. Giwa-Osagie OO. Nigeria has twelve million infertile persons. *Pharmanews* 2003; 25(7):48-9.
6. Osegbe DN, Amaku EO. The causes of male infertility in 504 consecutive Nigerian patients. *Int Urol Nephrol* 1985; 17:349.
7. Geidam A D, Yawe K D T, Adebayo A E A, Idrisa A. Hormonal profile of men investigated for infertility at the University of Maiduguri in northern Nigeria. *Singapore Med J* 2008; 49(7): 538-541
8. Aziz N, Agarwal A, Nallella KP, Thomas AJ Jr. Relationship between epidemiological features and aetiology of male infertility as diagnosed by a comprehensive infertility service provider. *Reprod Biomed Online* 2006; 12:209-14.
9. Idrisa A, Ojiji E, Tomfafi O, Kamara TB, Pindiga HU. Male contribution to infertility in Maiduguri, Nigeria. *Trop J Obstet Gynaecol* 2001; 18:87-90.
10. Akinloye O, Arowojolu AO, Shittu OB, Anetor JI. Cadmium toxicity: a possible cause of male infertility in Nigeria. *Reprod Biol* 2006, 6:17-30.
11. Enuh, H., Oragwu, C I., Okeke, C., Elu, E., & Orisakwe, OE. Semen Abnormality and Nigerian Herbal Remedies: A Preliminary Investigation. *The Internet Journal of Toxicology*, 2012; 8(2).
12. Obi E, Akunyili DN, Ekpo B Orisakwe OE. Heavy metal hazards of Nigerian herbal remedies. *Sci Tot Environ*. 2006; 369:35-41
13. Benoff S, Jacob A and Hurley I R 2000 Male infertility and environmental exposure to lead and cadmium; *Hum. Reprod.* 6 107-121
14. Jurasović J, Cvitković P, Pizent A, Colak B, Telisman S. Semen quality and reproductive endocrine function with regard to blood cadmium in Croatian male subjects. *Biometals* 2004, 17:735-743.
15. Telisman S, Colak B, Pizent A, Jurasović J, Cvitković P. Reproductive toxicity of low-level lead exposure in men. *Environ Res* 2007, 105:256-266.
16. Telisman S, Cvitković P, Jurasović J, Pizent A, Gavella M, Rocić B. Semen quality and reproductive endocrine function in relation to biomarkers of lead, cadmium, zinc and copper in men. *Environ Health Perspect* 2000, 108:45-53.
17. Hernández-Ochoa I, García-Vargas G, López-Carrillo L, Rubio-Andrade M, Morán-Martínez J, Cebrián ME, Quintanilla-Vega B: Low lead environmental exposure alters semen quality and sperm chromatin condensation in northern Mexico. *Reprod Toxicol* 2005, 20:221-228.
18. Giaccio L, Cicchella D., De Vivo B. , Lombardi G., De Rosa M. Does heavy metals pollution affects semen quality in men? A case of study in the metropolitan area of Naples (Italy), *Journal of Geochemical Exploration* 112 (2012) 218-225

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